

Media Processing and Pose Estimation in Physical Training

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Abstract—Media processing and pose estimation using computer vision are employed in this study to help athletes, yogis, and bodybuilders maintain proper posture while exercising. We can't always expect personal attention from the trainer when we're at a public gym, yoga studio, or training facility. However, the activities we engage in in these locations can have a negative impact on our health in the short and long term. Everyone can have the attention of their AI personal trainer to watch out for them and help them maintain improved posture during their workout with the use of Media Processing and position estimation in computer vision. The proposed system can also keep track of how many repetitions they've done and how many sets they've completed.

Keywords—Media Processing, AI, Pose Estimation, mediaPipe, Python, Computer Vision

I. INTRODUCTION

Physical training is something that should be approached with caution. Personal attention from an experienced individual or instructor is always required for these exercises. However, at a public gym, yoga studio, or training facility, we can't always demand a trainer's attention. We cannot put our health at danger by adopting poor postures. As a result, we always require someone to check our posture and count the repetitions so that we may concentrate on our breathing pattern and other elements. Here we introduce the AI personal trainer, which is always with us and can be downloaded to our laptops, smartphones, tablets, and other devices. The AI helper can assist us in maintaining our posture and reps. This is done using the help of computer vision and media processing in python.

II. BASIC TERMINOLOGIES USED

A. Mediapipe

MediaPipe is a framework for creating machine learning pipelines for time-series data such as video and audio. This cross-platform Framework is compatible with desktop/server, Android, iOS, and embedded devices such as the Raspberry Pi and Jetson Nano. MediaPipe Toolkit comprises the Framework and the Solutions. Here the mediaPipe landmarks are used to draw the pivot points of the human body. The angle of elbow is used to count the reps in this software. Angle is calculated using the function in mediaPipe. Fig 1. Shows the mediapipe process flowchart

B. OpenCV

OpenCV is that the leading open-source library for pc vision, image process and machine learning. OpenCV is released

Fig 1. MediaPipe process

under a BSD license and thence it's free for each educational and industrial use.

OpenCV is being employed for a wide selection of applications that include.

- Street read image sewing
- Automated examination and police work
- Robot and driver-less automotive navigation and management
- Medical image analysis

OpenCV is used in software to capture the image through the camera and process it for pose estimation. mediaPipe is used over the OpenCV for marking the pivot points. The output is displayed in OpenCV frame with sets and reps counted

Fig.2. Landmarks of human body

C. Pose Estimation

Human pose estimation and tracking is a computer vision task that includes detecting, associating, and tracking semantic key points'

There are three types of models for human body modeling:

- Kinematic Model
- Planar Model
- Volumetric Model

Fig 3. Depicts the above mentioned models

Fig.3. Types of human body modelling

We use Kinematic model here cause its more lightweight and faster. This helps us process the media more real-time. Kinematic model also meets our needs of pose estimation for physical training.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

[1] [1] OpenCV with OpenPose MobileNet for body posture detection. They have used this for finding the limitations of already existing systems.They have proposed OpenCV and implemented it for pose estimation. OpenCV is cheaper , Need less hardware and more effective in practical applications.

[2] computer vision is used to extract edge points using their algorithm and used it for sitting pose estimation. algorithm was able to obtain and measure sitting posture parameters and use it in assessing the sitting posture of a person.

[3] \ OpenCV, CNN network and COCO dataset for gym posture assistance using camera vision. They have used dataset to make machine learn from the existing training postures.

[4] A dataset of 6 Yoga asanas had been created using 15 individuals. A hybrid deep learning model was proposed using CNN and LSTM for Yoga recognition on real-time videos, the system can be implemented on a portable device for real-time predictions and self-training.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The Proposed System of personal AI assistant works in 3 phases. In the 1st phase we extract the live stream of the person using OpenCV and process them for next stage. In the second stage we process the frames of the stream using mediaPipe and mark the pivot points. The pivot points is marked using the already trained MediaPipe library in python.

In the next stage we calculate the angle of elbow using the angle function of the mediaPipe. This is used to count the number of reps and sets. The pose estimation using kinematic model in mediaPipe is used for this.

A. Extracting User Video Stream

The OpenCV library iin python is used for getting the video stream of users.The basic video processing is done using the help of the OpenCV library.OpenCv can be configured to acces the webcam in a laptop or a ny camera in smartphone and these sources are used in the next stages for further processeing.

B. Identify the Pivot points

The pivot points are identified using the mediaPipe library in python. The pivot points. MediaPipe is already trained for locating key landmarks of the body like head, knees, shoulder joints etc. These pivot points and the kinematic model is overlaid on the video stream.Fig 2. Shows the landmarks that are marked by the Mediaipipe and fig 4. Shows the real-time detection of these landmarks.

Fig.4. Realtime detection

C. Counting The Reps and Sets.

The angle of the pivot points marked by the media processing is used for finding the reps and sets of the user. In this system we use the elbow angles for identifying the number of biceps curls the user have done.

The curl form is found using the angle of the elbow as it is the pivot point for bicep curls. The rep is counted using the angle. If the angle is less than 30 degrees, then the curl is "UP" Stage and if the angle is greater than 160 and if the previous stage was "UP" then the stage is "DOWN". Fig 5. shows the angle of right elbow found using Mediapipe.

Fig.5. Finding angle of elbow

V.RESULT

In our system we use the user live video stream as a input and we process them for assisting them in their physical training. After we get the video, we process it using the mediaPipe for drawing the landmarks of the human body. Then we use the angle of the elbow and other logic to count the rep and sets. This helps the user to focus other aspects of training. Fig 6. Depicts the result of the proposed system.

The accuracy of sets is almost 100% as there aren't any comparison with images. Instead, it is compared with numerical values. The sets are completed once we get our reps to 12 until then the set is in progress. Once the reps exceed 12 the set is completed, and next set is in progress.

V.CONCLUSION

The system will combine fitness and technology to successfully bring advancement in tracking and acting as a personal trainer to the users without requiring the help of any actual trainer. It brings full-fledged flexibility to the user to perform exercise anytime throughout the day as per their availability of free time. The constant need for the attention of personal trainers in gyms is guided put by AI personal

Trainer. The counting of Reps and Sets by AI helps the users to focus on other aspects of the training.

Fig.6. Counting reps and sets

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

A system like these can replace personal trainers for correcting body posture and the need for their constant attention while performing exercises or yoga poses. The system can be featured by adding more exercises and yoga poses to the system. We can create a user portal that keeps a track and record of the data of their previous exercises and yoga performed in the system's database. Variation can be brought by adding sections for men, women, and children depending on their age group and segregating different sections based on the difficulties of the exercises. The system with all these features can be added as a daily routine to prevent injuries and muscle strains while performing exercises also track the counts of all exercises and keep a report of the users' performance.

VIII. REFERENCES

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